

Epicentre Location and Association of Events from P-wave on-set Times, Magnitude Estimation

Andreas Rosenberger*, Bob Crosby, Eli Ferguson, Martin Heeseman,
Brandon Leech, Melissa MacArthur, Angela Schlesinger, Liam Scholte,
Lu Wang and Yingsong Zheng

V2.1, Documentation for WARN,
July 2014 - May 2015, July - Aug 2018, Jan-March 2019

1 Introduction

Observational seismology has a large array of algorithms at its disposal to locate an earthquake from waveform recordings at a number of seismograph stations. The task in any case is to locate an event in three spatial coordinates (hypocentre), in general longitude, latitude, depth, and in time (origin time). Since different seismic phases travel with different propagation velocities through the earth, the identification of individual phases and their delays, which depend on the distance from the earthquake source location, already constrain origin time and source to station distance. In particular the location problem in two spatial coordinates (epicentre) and the determination of origin time is well posed. Determination of depth is in general not a well posed problem, due to the geometry of the problem where seismic stations are confined to the earth's surface.

The problem setting for Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) is different since the time needed to observe and analyze the full wave-form over the total duration of an earthquake cannot be afforded. It thus comes at no surprise that algorithms which determine the location of a source from just the first arrival times of a wave (in the case of earthquakes, the P-wave) have initially been developed in acoustical engineering (Friedlander, 1987; Schau and Robinson, 1987; Huang and Benesty, 2000; Pirinen, Pertilä, and Visa, 2003; Pirinen, 2006; Gillette and Silverman, 2008) rather than in seismology. Complete seismograms provide a lot more information than just first arrival times of a single phase.

A similar remark applies to algorithms proposed for estimating the final magnitude of an earthquake from just a few seconds of P-wave recordings. This approach remains controversial among seismologists and more recent research suggests that incorporating real-time displacement data from Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) may provide more robust estimates and updates while a large earthquake unfolds.

*andreas@arescon.com

2 Revisions to this Document

A significant revision, with a new section 6 and a revision of what has become section 7 was prompted

- by our observation that the direct grid search algorithm (section 5.1) in a "staggered grid" implementation is fast enough to compute in a real-time context. Its error tolerance and the fact that it can determine an epicentre from a minimum of three P-wave detections (as opposed to four for the linearized least squares algorithm, sect. 5.2) suggests that it can be used to prime other algorithms and that it is useful for an error recovery procedure.
- by the observation that with a staggered grid implementation parameter w in equation 3 cannot be implemented with a fixed value as originally suggested. Parameter σ , determining the "width" of the Gaussian is no longer independent of the grid resolution.
- by noting that while the direct grid search algorithm produces a solution independent of the choice of a particular reference sensor, its quality proxy, ΔT_{RMS} , has to be computed as average from all time differences of arrival (TDOA) combinations to be unique.
- by discussions within the group recognizing the need to define a process for error recovery when erroneous data have been associated with a seismic event. This error recovery algorithm is described in section 6.
- by the fact that the error recovery procedure can at the same time be used efficiently to determine if a new detection (or a set of detections) belong(s) to an ongoing event. This makes the initially proposed time-gating algorithm, where arrival time was checked against the theoretical travel-time from an established epicentre and earthquake origin time, obsolete.
- observing during tests that the linearized least squares algorithm can produce small ΔT_{RMS} values and large condition numbers γ at the same time. Section 6.2 was amended suggesting that solutions with large condition numbers are rejected. AR, 2018-08-12
- The concept of stepping epicentre location algorithms through a range of seismic P-wave velocities is expanded in section 4.1 which now precedes the presentation of epicentre location algorithms. With a foreseeable configuration of stations in the network this is intended to provide better solutions for deep ($h > 36km$) local earthquakes and for earthquakes with larger epicentral distances. AR, 2018-07-21
- To address the problem that tele-seismic events may be miss-located and miss-qualified as local or regional events a new section 10 was added. AR, 2019-01-31
- There was an omission in connection with equations 2 and 3 which could result in transferring the solution onto the wrong hyperbola branch. In an earlier version this was just discussed in the following text, it is now emphasized rearranging equation 3. AR, 2019-03-21
- Extensive testing has prompted several changes:
 - The condition number threshold for the linearized least squares solution, discussed in section 6.2 can be lowered to 30. The same is true for the error recovery procedure discussed in section 6.3 where the threshold parameter is lowered from 0.8 to to 0.6.

- The direct grid search algorithm (sect. 5.1) is implemented in a staggered form, going from an initially coarse grid to smaller grid cells in the subsequent iteration. The cells neighbouring the cell with the highest probability should be included in the next iteration.
- Distance calculations for both location algorithms should assume a hypocentral depth of $25km$ to provide better solutions for local events in distances of less than $100km$. This affects primarily the direct grid search algorithm but also the quality parameter computations (Sect. 6) for both, the direct grid search and the linearized least squares solution. It involves *only source to receiver distance calculations*, inter station distances are not affected.

AR, 2019-03-22

3 Seismometer Data

A driver module for the seismometers has been developed by John Dorocicz (ONC). This driver will autonomously detect seismic events in real time and generate the following parametric data:

- the P-wave arrival time (format to be determined) with milli-second precision. The resolution depends on the digitization sampling interval.
- τ_p^{max} , four seconds after the P-wave arrival, one floating point value for the maximum observed period of the vertical component signal in seconds.
- P_d , four seconds after the P-wave arrival, one floating point value for the maximum displacement amplitude of the vertical component signal in centimetres.
- JMA instrumental intensity amplitude, a_0 , every second after the P-wave arrival, a floating point value in physical units of cm/s^2 . In the absence of a detection a_0 will be reported as "heart-beat" signal at full second time ticks. With the detection of a P-wave a_0 will be reported in one second time intervals after detection time and labelled as "P". With the arrival of the S-wave (or loss of P) labelling will change to "S". 120 seconds after P-wave detection time a_0 is re-set and returns to "heart-beat" reporting mode.

4 Problem Statement: Epicentre Location, Origin Time

When a minimum number of N seismometers has reported the arrival time of a P-wave, the seismometer locations (as two-dimensional coordinates) and the time differences of arrival (TDOA) at the respective stations are the observed quantities. From N stations

$$\binom{N}{2} = \frac{N \cdot (N - 1)}{2} \quad (1)$$

TDOAs are available but only $N - 1$ are *independent*. Thus for exact, noise free data 3 P-wave detections would provide two independent TDOA measurements, sufficient to constrain the two unknown epicentre coordinates. If the data are contaminated with random measurement errors all $\frac{N(N-1)}{2}$ TDOAs are independent (assuming that the errors are independent) and an optimum solution can be derived from the over-determined problem where now, for the three station example, three TDOA measurements are used to compute the two unknowns.

It is practically impossible to additionally determine earthquake source depth (the hypocentre) with TDOA measurements from a surface array of seismometers.

4.1 Estimating Apparent P-wave Velocity

A well written summary of the role of seismic velocities in the earthquake location problem can be found in Havskov, Bormann, and Schweitzer, 2011. While a P-wave velocity of 6200 m/s is adequate for events in less than 36 km depth for epicentral distances up to 100-200 km where the P_g phase is generally the first arrival, deeper local events ($h > 36km$) are generally associated with an apparent P-wave velocity of 8200 m/s in South-West BC. The same would be true for seismic events with epicentral distances greater than 150 – 200km. Here the seismic P_n phase, having travelled through deeper parts of the crust may be the first arrival. Havskov, Bormann, and Schweitzer, 2011 give a "rule of thumb" formula to estimate the cross-over distance, the distance when the faster P_n overtakes the P_g phase as $x_{co} \approx 5z_m$ and with a crustal thickness $z_m \approx 36km$ this comes out to about 180km.

The current configuration of the network of seismic stations has a north-west/south-east extension of about 400km, and a south-west/north-east extension of about 120km. For events with epicentres in a south-east or north-west direction *and outside the array*, P-waves will have travelled past the cross-over distance to stations on the opposite side of the array and the best (see section 6) epicentre estimate will be based on a velocity between 6000 and 8500 m/s which will minimize the TDOA residual.

The same would be true for deep, local earthquakes with smaller epicentral distances where apparent P-wave velocities of over 7000 m/s may provide the best result.

Extending the computation for both location algorithms presented below and stepping the seismic P-wave velocity in steps of 500m/s from 6000m/s to 8000m/s should yield a minimum ΔT_{RMS} (see equation 20 and 21) for the most appropriate approximate velocity and -for a local event- also be an indication for hypocentral depth.

A practical approach could start the algorithms with an assumed P-wave velocity of 7000 m/s and subsequently re-compute the solution with 6500 m/s. If ΔT_{RMS} did improve, then also compute the solution for 6000 m/s and test again for an improvement.

If the trial with 6500 m/s did not improve the solution based on 7000 m/s, the velocity would be stepped in the other direction and a trial with 7500 m/s is computed. If that further improved the quality, a last trial with 8000 m/s would be checked for its performance. In this way all reasonable approximations to the P-wave velocity would have been tested while limiting the additional computational effort to a factor of 3 compared to a solution based on one single velocity.

This approach would also lend itself to an implementation with parallel computing.

4.2 Sources of Errors

Errors in the measurements are predominantly timing errors, either caused by in-accurate instrument clocks or errors introduced by the detection algorithm which determines the onset of the P-wave with an

unknown margin of error.

Additionally errors in the “model”, in this case assumed P-wave velocities, which are needed to convert travel times to distances introduce a bias, affecting all measurements in a similar way. In particular, origin time of the earthquake as determined from epicentre to station distances and apparent P-wave propagation velocity is strongly affected by error in the assumed apparent P-wave velocity.

5 Proposed Earthquake Epicentre Location Methods

5.1 Direct Grid Search

This procedure is most likely the easiest one to understand, its basic implementation is straight forward. However, the method is inherently slow, to serve its purpose within an EEW system it would have to make use of parallel processing to provide timely epicentres and origin times. The method degrades gracefully with errors in the data and the velocity model.

The region of interest is overlain by a longitude, latitude grid of of appropriate resolution.

From P-wave detections times from N (at least three) seismometer sites the potential source location can then be established in a grid search from the time-differences of arrival

$$\delta t_{ij} = t_i - t_j, \quad i = 1, \dots, N - 1; \quad j = i + 1, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

where t_i is the detected P-wave arrival time at site i .

For every grid-point s (viewed as a trial source location) one then solves the “hyperbolical intersection” forward problem and computes for each pair of sensors:

$$P(s)_{ij} = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{w}(\Delta T s - \|\delta t_{ij}\|)^2\right), \quad i = 1, \dots, N - 1; \quad j = i + 1, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

For $\delta t_{ij} > 0$ the calculated TDOA for a trial source at s becomes $\Delta T s = t_{si} - t_{sj}$, for $\delta t_{ij} < 0$ $\Delta T s = t_{sj} - t_{si}$ (note that indexes j and i are interchanged).

t_{si} and t_{sj} are the travel-times from the candidate source location at the source grid-point s to seismometer sites i and j respectively. Based on an *assumed* P-wave velocity v_p , $t_{si} = \Delta_{si}/v_p$ and $t_{sj} = \Delta_{sj}/v_p$.

Δ_{sl} is the distance from the trial source location to station l and it is suggested to assume a hypocentral depth of $h = 25 \cdot 10^3 m$ and to compute Δ_{sl} in a flat earth approximation as $\Delta_{sl} = \sqrt{d_{sl}^2 + h^2}$, with d_{sl} being the epicentral distance.

The remaining parameter w , in terms of a Gaussian distribution $w = 2\sigma^2$, is a scaling parameter which reflects the uncertainties in the travel-time and arrival time difference estimates and determines the

width of the Gaussian

Since the Gaussian must reach over several grid cells, σ is dependent on the dimension of a grid cell.

In a staggered grid implementation σ (in units of seconds) can be determined approximately as

$$\sigma \approx \frac{111 \cdot 10^3 \cdot \delta_{lat}}{v_p},$$

where δ_{lat} is the latitude width of a grid cell in degrees and v_p is P-wave velocity in m/s . The approximate great circle distance over 1° is about $111km$.

Figure 1: The (under-determined) two station (red triangles) source location problem. The source (white star) must lie on the hyperbola branch closer to the station which detected the arrival first. Employing the Gauss function from Eq. 3 introduces an uncertainty which grows with the distance of the source from the stations. From the TDOAs of three stations one can construct $\frac{3 \times 2}{2} = 3$ hyperbolas which will intersect at the source location.

The basic principle is illustrated in figure 1 for two stations where the problem is under-determined. The possible source locations for a given TDOA from two stations define a hyperbola in 2-D space. Note that δt_{ij} in equation 2 can be *positive* or *negative* depending whether the P-wave arrived first at station i or at station j . The sign thus determines which of the two possible hyperbola branches defines the possible source locations.

The correct branch of the hyperbola is selected by optionally interchanging the indices i and j in Eq. 3 so that $\delta t_{ji} = \|\delta_{ij}\| \geq 0$. This assures that the arrival time order for the trial source at s is consistent with the arrival time order at the respective station pair.

For each grid point s the values $P(s)_{ij}$ from equation 3 are added for each station pair i, j , the grid-point with the maximum value after going through all station pairs gives a maximum likelihood estimate of the source location. A map of the grid is also often referred to as “spatial histogram” (Moni and

Rickard, 2009). With N detections from individual seismometer sites $\binom{N}{2} = \frac{N!}{2(N-2)!} = \frac{N(N-1)}{2}$ combinations of travel-time differences from the respective sites pairs enter the calculation, thus evaluating also redundant (in the case of error free data) information. The grid search algorithm is known to be very robust in the presence of errors and the grid can be partitioned for parallel computing. Additionally a staggered grid approach can be used where initially a large, course grid is used to compute an approximate epicentre, an area around this initial estimate is overlain by a smaller, finer grid, where the computation is repeated. Parallelization based on individual station pairs is also a possible strategy where equation 3 is evaluated for each i, j in a separate parallel process.

An example with data recorded by the Japanese KiK-Net from the March 9, 2011, Mw 7.4 foreshock of the Tohoku (Japan) earthquake is given in figure 2. The source/station geometry is typical for an off-shore earthquake. The maximum uncertainty in the location extends perpendicular to the main extension of the seismic station array. To make this as realistic as possible, P-wave arrivals were detected in the KiK-Net data with the algorithm proposed by Rosenberger, 2010. The seven earliest arrivals are used to compute a spatial histogram with equation 3. The histogram is normalized with the number of contributing combinations (here: $7 \cdot 6/2 = 21$), the scale shows that over 90% of the individual contributions "agree" at the epicentre. It should be stressed that in this particular case with the given source/receiver geometry, seven detections are the minimum needed to generate a plausible epicentre and the uncertainty expressed in the large area covered by the 0.8 contour is still large.

Figure 2: P-wave detections from seven KiK-Net stations (red triangles) have been used to generate a spatial histogram according to equation 3. The epicentre, determined as the location of the maximum value of the histogram is marked with a white circle, also shown are the epicentres as determined by the USGS and JMA. The white star marks the probably most accurate epicentre after Shao, Ji, and Zhao, 2011. Grid resolution is $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ (100×120 grid nodes).

5.1.1 Prerequisites

Distances have to be calculated from geodetic coordinates on a reference ellipsoid. A suitable algorithm Vincenty, 1975, is available (as Matlab or C-code, see Rosenberger, 2014).

Vincenty's algorithm is also documented in a Wikipedia article: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vincenty%27s_formulae (last accessed Oct. 2014)

5.1.2 Estimating Origin Time

Origin time is particularly sensitive to the assumed (or estimated) P-wave velocity. Once the epicentre has been determined travel-times to all stations which have detected the event can be calculated and origin time can be computed from a mean value (see eq. 17).

5.1.3 Real-time Computations

In an ensuing earthquake new detection data are generated every time the propagating P-wave arrives at a more distant station. It is suggested that the computation starts with a minimum of three detection times.

With $N - 1$ stations already processed every new detection at station n requires recalculating the grid according to equation 3

$$P(s)_{n,j}, \quad for \quad j = 1, ..N - 1 \quad (4)$$

and a re-calculation of origin time.

5.1.4 Event epicenters outside the region covered by the grid

The region of interest (see section 8) covered by the grid will naturally be constrained by the final network of stations and by the scope of WARN. Any earthquake with an epicenter outside this region will still produce a direct grid search solution which will likely lie on one of the boundary grid cells. In addition to a probably large residual T_{RMS} value (see section 6) a grid search resulting in a calculated epicentre on a grid boundary cell is an indication for a non-regional event and should be dismissed.

5.2 Linearized Least Squares

The second method suggested follows Gillette and Silverman, 2008 as a variation of what was proposed earlier in Friedlander, 1987 as "closed form" or "one step" source location from time-differences of arrival (TDOA). The basic algorithm evaluates the $N - 1$ non-redundant TDOAs for the two source coordinates from $N > 3$ sensors which have detected the signal. The TDOAs can be directly derived from the reported P-wave arrival times at each sensor. For the algorithm of Gillette and Silverman, 2008 TDOAs need to be converted to distance differences.

The method defines a reference sensor with coordinates x_0, y_0 and defines the TDOA from sensor m with respect to this reference sensor

$$\delta t_{m,0} = (\Delta_{s,m} - \Delta_{s,0})/v_p, \quad (5)$$

$\Delta_{s,m}$ and $\Delta_{s,0}$ are the source to sensor distances for sensor m and the reference sensor respectively, v_p is the wave propagation velocity. The source distance difference of the reference sensor and sensor m can be directly computed from the measured TDOA $\delta t_{m,0}$ (as in eq. 2) and the apparent P-wave propagation velocity v_p :

$$d_{m,0} = \Delta_{s,m} - \Delta_{s,0} = \delta t_{m,0} v_p \quad (6)$$

Gillette and Silverman, 2008 express the source location problem as a set of linear equations

$$\mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}_s = \mathbf{w} \quad (7)$$

with

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} x_0 - x_1 & y_0 - y_1 & d_{1,0} \\ x_0 - x_2 & y_0 - y_2 & d_{2,0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_0 - x_N & y_0 - y_N & d_{N,0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where x_m, y_m are the coordinates of sensor m and $d_{m,0}$ is defined from equation 6.

$$\mathbf{x}_s = \begin{bmatrix} x_s \\ y_s \\ R_0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

\mathbf{x}_s has the source coordinates as first two components, R_0 is what Friedlander, 1987 calls the ‘‘nuisance’’ variable, the distance from the source to the reference sensor.

$$\mathbf{w} = \begin{bmatrix} w_{1,0} \\ w_{2,0} \\ \vdots \\ w_{N,0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

with

$$w_{m,0} = \frac{1}{2}(d_{m,0}^2 - x_m^2 + x_0^2 - y_m^2 + y_0^2), \quad (11)$$

where $d_{m,0}$ is from Equation 6, x_m, y_m are the coordinates of station m .

The solution is obtained computing the matrix inverse \mathbf{A}^\dagger ,

$$\mathbf{x}_s = \mathbf{A}^\dagger \mathbf{w} \quad (12)$$

Deviating from Gillette and Silverman, 2008 it is suggested to compute the inverse with a singular value decomposition (SVD):

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^T \quad (13)$$

$\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}_{N \times 3}$ is of rank 3, with a maximum of three non-zero singular values, thus matrix dimensions are

$\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}_{N \times 3}$, $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{R}_{3 \times 3}$, $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}_{3 \times 3}$.

The SVD inverse is

$$\mathbf{A}^\dagger = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{U}^\mathbf{T}, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/\sigma_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\sigma_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\sigma_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Using an SVD for matrix inversion is motivated by the fact that for arbitrary source/receiver geometries the matrix \mathbf{A} may have a high condition number

$$\gamma = \frac{\sigma_0}{\sigma_2} \quad (16)$$

(the problem is ill-conditioned, meaning that small errors in the data may cause dis-proportionate large errors in the solution).

An example, using the same data as for the generation of figure 2 is shown in figure 3. The epicentre as computed with the least squares method is shown with a blue circle together with the USGS, JMA, Shao, Ji, and Zhao, 2011 epicentres, and the spatial histogram solution (white circle).

Figure 3: P-wave detections from seven KiK-Net stations (red triangles) have been used to additionally compute the linearized least squares solution (LLS) for the example shown in Figure 2. The LLS epicentre is marked by a blue circle.

5.2.1 Prerequisites

The LLS method is based on a plane Cartesian coordinate system and thus requires a projection from geodetic longitude, latitude data to Mercator or Universal Transversal Mercator (UTM) coordinates. A library with suitable projection algorithms is Proj4 (<http://trac.osgeo.org/proj/>, last accessed 2014-07-08), which is available with several language bindings.

A library function to compute the singular value decomposition is part of the standard linear algebra packages (i.e. the GNU scientific library).

5.2.2 Real-time Computations

The algorithm needs a minimum of four stations to have detected and reported the P-wave arrival to compute a solution for three non-redundant TDOAs. Any additional detection requires the re-computation of the augmented set of linear equations in 12.

However, to include redundant TDOAs, the LLS algorithm should be iterated through all possible reference sensors $r = 1, \dots, N$, resetting matrix \mathbf{A} (eq. 8) and vector \mathbf{w} (eqs. 10, 11) and solving equation 12 with respect to reference sensor r .

For each solution a quality proxy can be established evaluating equation 18 (see section 6) and the solution yielding the smallest product $C(r) = \gamma(r) \cdot \Delta T_{RMS}(r)$, of condition number (eq. 16) and residual error (eq. 18) can be chosen.

5.2.3 Events with epicenters outside WARN's region of interest

Different from the direct grid search, the linearized least squares method will in general find epicenters for events which are not regional in the sense that they lie outside WARN's region of interests as defined by the grid for the direct grid search algorithm (see section 8). Those events should be recognized as "non regional" and should not be reported.

5.3 Origin Time

Origin time should be computed as mean value, taking all distances from stations that have contributed to the epicentre location and dividing by the assumed P-wave velocity v_p

$$T_0 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N [t_i - d_{i,s}/v_p], \quad (17)$$

t_i is the reported P-wave arrival time at station i , $d_{i,s}$ is its distance to the epicentre.

The LLS solution does not offer an obvious means to optimize the solution in regard to the P-wave velocity, origin times obtained from the LLS solution will be biased from errors in v_p .

5.4 Comments, Recommendations

The linearized least squares solution is fast to compute and directly suitable in a real-time context. On the other hand, it offers little to immediately assess the quality of a solution, which strongly depends on the source, station-array geometry, the accuracy of the detection times and a good estimate on the

apparent P-wave velocity (which can vary from ~ 6200 to $\sim 8200m/s$ for regional earthquakes). The only observable in the LLS solution is the condition number $\text{cond}(\mathbf{A}) = \sigma_0/\sigma_2$ of matrix \mathbf{A} . With small errors in the arrival times condition numbers in the order of 10^1 will likely produce reasonably good epicentres. With condition numbers in the order of 10^2 the solution becomes un-reliable. The solution shown in figure 3 produced a condition number of 12.7.

6 Quality of a Solution

To obtain a quality proxy for both, the direct grid-search and LLS solutions, it is suggested to evaluate the root mean square (RMS) TDOA residuals ΔT_{RMS} for an epicentre solution. Here the measured time-differences of arrival, $\delta t_{i,j}$ are compared with the theoretical TDOAs, $\sigma_{i,j}$ based on the current epicentre and (in case of the LLS algorithm) reference sensor r :

$$\Delta T_{RMS}(r) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{m=1}^{N-1} (\|\delta t_{m,r}\| - \|\sigma_{m,r}\|)^2}, \quad (18)$$

where $\delta t_{m,r}$ is from equation 2 and

$$\sigma_{m,r} = d_{m,r}/v_p \quad (19)$$

are the theoretical TDOAs derived from the current epicentre where $d_{m,r} = \Delta_{s,m} - \Delta_{s,r}$ is the distance difference of sensor m and reference sensor r to the epicentre solution at s , as in equation 6. The symbol $\|\cdot\|$ indicates "absolute value".

For the *theoretical* TDOAs the computation of $\Delta_{s,m}$ and $\Delta_{s,r}$ should assume a source depth of $25km$ as described in section 5.1.

6.1 Quality of the direct grid search solution

Since the direct grid search epicenter solution evaluates also the redundant (for error free data) time differences of arrival (TDOA) a unique proxy for the quality of a solution can be calculated similar as in equation 18, also assuming hypocentral depth as $25km$, as RMS value from all $N(N-1)/2$ TDOA combinations

$$\Delta T_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{N(N-1)} \sum_{m=1}^{N-1} \sum_{n=m+1}^N (\|\delta t_{m,n}\| - \|\sigma_{m,n}\|)^2}, \quad (20)$$

Note that the "maximum likelihood" value $\max [P(s)_{i,j}]$ as the *normalized* maximum of the spatial histogram is not suited as a quality parameter for the direct grid search method since it will degrade while detections from more distant stations are becoming part of the solution.

6.2 Quality of the linearized least squares solution

In section 5.2.2 it was suggested that the best LLS solution, depending on the choice of the reference sensor r , is selected as the one yielding the smallest product of condition number and TDOA residual

$$C = \gamma(r) \cdot \Delta T_{RMS}(r). \quad (21)$$

This value is a unique quality proxy for the LLS solution.

In general C should not be larger than 10^1 .

In any case solutions with a condition number $\gamma(r) > 30$ should be **rejected**.

6.3 Consistency Test and Error Recovery

Any epicentre solution and the associated detections from $N \geq 3$ sensors can be tested for errors in the data, also to prevent erroneous parameters, determined from the seismic waveforms to become part of a magnitude estimate. It is suggested to compute a direct grid search (DGS) solution initially. Since DGS is largely tolerant against erroneous data any subset of raw events may still produce a DGS solution.

It then needs to be established which of the raw events belong to the sub-set and form TDOAs consistent with the DGS epicentre.

With $\delta t_{i,j}$ and $\sigma_{i,j}$ from equations 2 and 19 the actual and theoretical (expected) time-differences of arrival for the new epicentre can be compared for all N raw events:

$$d_{i,j} = |||\delta t_{i,j}|| - ||\sigma_{i,j}||, \quad i = 1, \dots, N - 1; \quad j = i + 1, \dots, N, \quad (22)$$

including the redundant (for error free data) TDOA combinations ($|| \cdot ||$ again indicates "absolute value").

Any $d_{i,j} > 1.0s$ would indicate that either detection time t_i or detection time t_j is not consistent with the epicentre solution.

Assume that S_i is the score-card for event i in the set of N events in the Event-bucket and initially $S_i = 0, i = 1, \dots, N$.

Any result $d_{i,j} > 1.0$ for detections t_i and t_j in equation 22 would trigger an increment of score-cards S_i and S_j by 1.

Then one erroneous detection time t_m in the set should theoretically give a score of $S_m = N - 1$, since this detection time was part of computing $d_{i,j}$ (from equation 22) $N - 1$ times. A practical approach would accept events with scores $S_i \leq [0.6(N - 1)]$ as being associated with the new epicentre; $[\cdot]$ is the symbol for the *floor* function..

7 Event Association

With an established epicentre and origin time from either a minimum of three detections in the case of the spatial histogram method, or four detections for the LLS solution, all later detections can be subjected

to the *Consistency* test from section 6.3. Only detections which generate TDOAs $\|\delta t_{i,j}\|$ within 1 second of their expected values $\|\sigma_{i,j}\|$ are thus associated with the current seismic event.

Un-associated detections should not be directly dismissed but rather queued and subjected to a trial epicentre location process to determine if a second (or third) seismic event has occurred while processing the current one.

7.1 Terminology

An "event" is a single sensor detection with its associated data, P-wave detection time and magnitude relevant parameters ($\tau_p^{max}, P_d, JMA a_0$) as they become available. In trying to avoid suggesting any particular implementation we will use the term "bucket" for a data structure which can hold events and their associated data (see 3). There is one (raw) Event-bucket and any number (there may be none) of Seismic-Event-buckets. Seismic-Event-buckets are labelled with origin time, epicentre and a magnitude estimate.

7.2 From Events to Earthquakes

Raw events, as they are reported, are gathered in the Event-bucket where they expire after 120 seconds (this should be an adjustable parameter). Assuming that there are initially no seismic events pending there will be no "active" Seismic-Event-buckets. Any event, reported from any of the stations will arrive in the Event-bucket. As soon as the Event-bucket holds a minimum of three events, the Associator tries to locate an epicentre from the TDOAs of the three events with the grid-search algorithm.

A successful association would be indicated by a $\Delta T_{RMS} < 2.0s$ (eq. 18).

7.2.1 If it succeeds

... the three events are moved to a new Seismic-Event-bucket.

Any additional events arriving in the Event-bucket are tested

- if their arrival time is consistent with the TDOAs of the set of events in any Seismic-Event-bucket (in general there may be more than one).

The test described in 6.3 is an efficient tool to test the augmented set of events:

- A new DGS epicentre which includes the new datum is computed,
- events with high scores S_i are removed from the Seismic-Event-bucket.
- an updated epicentre solution, with both the grid-search and the LLS algorithm (if $N > 3$) is computed and tested if it improves the previous solution:
 - An improvement in case of the LLS algorithm would be indicated by a TDOA residual ΔT_{RMS} (eq. 18) less or equal to the one from the previous solution accompanied by a condition number under 30 (see eq. 16).
 - In case of the grid-search algorithm (5.1) the maximum (non-normalized) histogram value should increase and the associated ΔT_{RMS} should not increase.

All events passing the tests become the updated set of datums for the respective Seismic-Event-bucket. Subsequently the new averages for the event magnitude based on τ_p^{max} and P_d values are computed. A new JMA Intensity magnitude is computed based on the maximum a_0 values from each event over the last 10 seconds. The new magnitudes, epicentre, origin time are assigned to the respective Seismic-Event-bucket.

7.2.2 If it fails

- the event(s) may pertain to a tele-seismic event (every event outside WARN's region of interest),
- the event may be spurious, e.g. not a seismic event.
- the event may be from a new earthquake, possibly an aftershock.

Events older than 120 seconds are removed from the Event-bucket.

As long as LLS and grid-search epicentres have not converged to within less than $80km$ WARN should not report an earthquake.

8 Regional Focus

WARN intends to establish the basis for a regional EEWs. This region will initially be constrained by the network of deployed seismic instruments. Based on planned deployments and probable access to NRCan instrumentation it is suggested to limit the region initially to the contiguous area between longitudes -130° and -123° and latitudes 48° and 51.5° . This area covers the Nootka Fracture Zone (NFZ) and most of the subduction zone on the west coast of Vancouver Island.

Figure 5: Simulation of the 2004 M6.1 NFZ earthquake. A first epicentre can be established 12 seconds after origin time with three stations (red circle is the P-wavefront). One second later a fourth station reports and the first LLS epicentre (blue triangle) can be computed. The LLS and grid-search epicentres converge 15 seconds after origin time when six stations have detected the earthquake. ONC assets are marked as red triangles, the yellow triangles are NRCan strong motion instruments.

Figure 5 shows the suggested area, discretized $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ for the grid-search algorithm (140×70 grid points).

9 Magnitude Estimation

While many authors agree that τ_p^{max} and P_d are useful parameters for the estimation of earthquake magnitude from the first few seconds of the P-wave record, significant differences exist in the implementation of the respective computations (filters, observation time interval, etc.) and the proposed scaling relationships. This is an area of active research and in consequence there is no single, generally accepted set of methods. Additionally seismologists engaged in EEW propose regional scaling relationships which are supposed to address different tectonic settings.

9.1 τ_p^{max} Algorithm

The event processing module of the Associator takes the reported τ_p^i value of each event i , calculates

$$m_i = \log_{10}(\tau_p^i) \quad (23)$$

and the average from all N reports

$$\bar{m} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N m_i \quad (24)$$

(c.f. Wurman, Allen, and Lombard, 2007, par. 23).

I would recommend to use the *median* value instead, as Yamada and Mori, 2009, suggest. The *median* is more robust with a small number of samples.

This averaging (or using the median value) is justified since τ_p^{max} is supposed to be independent of the epicentral/hypocentral distance of the respective station. (Theoretically all instruments should report identical τ_p^{max} values).

The predicted magnitude (based on a scaling relationship validated for Northern California) after Wurman, Allen, and Lombard, 2007 then becomes (\bar{m} can be negative):

$$M = c_0 + c_1 \bar{m} \quad (25)$$

with $c_0 = 5.22$ and $c_1 = 6.66$.

Lockman and Allen, 2007, give two relations for the Pacific North-West

$$M_{1Hz-low-pass} = 6.7 + 6.1\bar{m} \quad (26)$$

$$M_{5Hz-low-pass} = 4.8 + 4.7\bar{m}, \text{ if greater 5.0 use 1Hz formula} \quad (27)$$

which are computed from different spectral bands of the signal.

I suggest to use the relation in equation 25 of Wurman, Allen, and Lombard, 2007 developed from the earthquake catalogue for Northern California.

9.2 P_d Algorithm

The displacement parameter P_d however depends on distance (Wu et al., 2007, eq.1) and Wurman, Allen, and Lombard, 2007 (par.24) are inconsistent (or ambiguous in their phrasing) in suggesting to average individual P_d^i values reported from stations i at *different* epicentral/hypocentral distances.

Magnitude estimates for an *individual* event i are calculated after Kuyuk and Allen, 2013

$$M_i = c_0 \log_{10}(P_d^i) + c_1 \log_{10}(R_i) + c_2 \quad (28)$$

with $c_0 = 1.23$, $c_1 = 1.38$ and $c_2 = 5.39$.

R_i is the epicentral distance of station i in *km*, P_d^i is in units of *cm*. According to Kuyuk and Allen, 2013 this relationship is valid *globally* and not restricted to one particular tectonic setting.

I would also suggest to calculate a *median* magnitude from all associated events.

As long as τ_p^{max} and P_d based magnitudes are more than 2 units different WARN should not report an earthquake.

9.3 JMA Intensity Magnitude

The method proposed by Yamamoto et al., 2008 is experimental and intended to overcome latencies associated with JMA's current method of establishing event magnitude (Hoshiba and Ozaki, 2014). Rydelek and Kim, 2010 found that the method works satisfactory with data from Korea but point out that attenuation and site specific parameters would have to be established from data for the respective tectonic region.

According to Yamamoto et al., 2008, eq.4, *Instrumental* intensity is calculated for every station i and every reported JMA $a_0^i(t)$ value (values are reported every second after the P-wave detection time)

$$I_i(t) = 2\log_{10}(a_0^i(t)) + 0.94 \quad (29)$$

and an Intensity magnitude estimate is calculated from the scaling relationship

$$M_I^i(t) = I_i(t)/2 + \log_{10}(R_i) + \pi T_i 0.0088 + b \quad (30)$$

Where R_i is distance from epicentre (km), $T_i = R_i/v_p$ is travel-time, $v_p \approx 6.2\text{km/s}$, b is a site correction term, which we would have to set to zero. The travel-time dependent term is based on the attenuation of seismic waves experimentally determined for Japan.

With Intensity magnitude estimates from several stations I suggest to compute a *median* value based on the last reported values $M_I^i(t)$. Since by construction, JMA a_0 values can only increase over time (asymptotically approaching some final value), so will the reported $M_I^i(t)$ value.

I propose to implement the method in an experimental fashion and, at this time, not to include magnitude estimates based on JMA M_I in the final estimate. Instrumental intensity $I(t)$ is a useful parameter for post earthquake damages estimates, its maximum values should be recorded.

10 Discrimination of Tele-Seismic Events

Deep Earthquakes, even in distances larger than 1000km may trigger a number of detections in the network. Kuyuk et al., 2014 proposed to exploit the fact that distant earthquakes in general register with a lower frequency content than local and regional earthquakes, resulting in larger observed period values τ_p^{max} combined with relatively small P-wave peak displacements P_d , a concept that has also been applied in a similar way by Zollo et al., 2010 for the Italian EEW system.

Kuyuk et al., 2014 compute the *mean* of all reported P_d and τ_p^{max} values and evaluate the function

$$F = K + \alpha \cdot \log_{10}(\overline{\tau_p^{max}}) + \beta \cdot \log_{10}(\overline{P_d}) \quad (31)$$

with

$$K = 32.75$$

$$\alpha = -24.75$$

$$\beta = 8.78$$

The units of $\overline{\tau_p^{max}}$ are seconds, $\overline{P_d}$ is in cm.

If eq. 31 evaluates to $F < 0$ the event is classified as tele-seismic.

Hartog et al., 2016 have modified this concept after testing it with earthquakes registered on the Pacific Northwest networks. For an event to qualify as tele-seismic they require additionally

$$\log_{10}(\overline{\tau_p^{max}}) > -0.1 \quad (32)$$

so that only events with an average $\overline{\tau_p^{max}} > 0.8$ are subjected to the test in equation 31.

It is suggested, with a small number of detections, to use the *median* values rather than the *mean* values of the reported τ_p^{max} and P_d . The mean or median values should be updated with new additional detections and the tests in eqns. 32 and 31 should be re-evaluated.

11 Concluding Remarks

What was described in the preceding sections is in total the minimum functionality of a system processing seismic P-wave detections which are assumed to be provided directly from a network of “smart” seismometers. Existing seismic acquisition systems, such as [Antelope](#) or [Seiscomp](#) provide a large variety of detection, association, location and magnitude estimation algorithms but are not geared to provide fast solutions suitable for EEW systems. This may change in the future. Still, the problems associated with latencies, out-of-sequence data, and data drop-outs remain when full waveform digital data have to be telemetered to a central processing facility for analysis. (c.f. Behr et al., 2015).

References

- Behr, Yannik et al. (2015). “Anatomy of an Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) Alert: Predicting Time Delays for an End-to-End EEW System”. In: *SRL* 86.3, pp. 830–840. DOI: [10.1785/0220140179](https://doi.org/10.1785/0220140179).
- Friedlander, B. (1987). “A passive localization algorithm and its accuracy analysis”. In: *IEEE J. Ocean Eng.* OE-12.1, pp. 234–245.
- Gillette, M. D. and H. F. Silverman (2008). “A linear closed-form algorithm for source localization from time-differences of arrival”. In: *IEEE Signal Process. Lett.* 15. See comment: Wei and Ye, 2008, pp. 1–4. DOI: [10.1109/LSP.2007.910324](https://doi.org/10.1109/LSP.2007.910324).
- Hartog, J. Renate et al. (Aug. 2016). “Earthquake Early Warning: ShakeAlert in the Pacific Northwest”. In: *BSSA* 106.4, pp. 1875–1886. DOI: [10.1785/0120150261](https://doi.org/10.1785/0120150261).
- Havskov, Jens, Peter Bormann, and Johannes Schweitzer (2011). “Information Sheet, Seismic Source Location”. In: *New Manual of Seismic Observatory Practice*. Postdam, Germany: GFZ, Postdam. DOI: [10.2312/GFZ](https://doi.org/10.2312/GFZ).
- Hoshiya, M. and T. Ozaki (2014). “Earthquake Early Warning and Tsunami Warning of the Japan Meteorological Agency, and Their Performance in the 2011 off the Pacific Coast of Tohoku Earthquake (Mw 9.0)”. In: *Early Warning for Geological Disasters*. Ed. by F. Wenzel and J. Zschau. Advanced Technologies in Earth Sciences. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 1–28. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-642-12233-0_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-12233-0_1).

- Huang, Yiteng and Jacob Benesty (2000). “Passive acoustic source location for video camera steering”. In: *Proc IEEE Intl. Conf. ASSP, Istanbul, Turkey*.
- Kuyuk, H. Serdar et al. (2014). “Designing a Network-Based Earthquake Early Warning Algorithm for California: ElarmS-2”. In: *BSSA* 104, pp. 162–173. DOI: [10.1785/0120130146](https://doi.org/10.1785/0120130146).
- Kuyuk, H.S. and R.M. Allen (2013). “A Global Approach to Provide Magnitude Estimates for Earthquake Early Warning Alerts”. In: *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 40.24, 63296333. DOI: [10.1002/2013GL058580](https://doi.org/10.1002/2013GL058580).
- Lockman, Andrew B. and Richard M. Allen (2007). “Magnitude-Period scaling relations for Japan and the Pacific Northwest: Implications for Earthquake Early Warning”. In: *BSSA* 97.1B, pp. 140–150. DOI: [10.1785/0120040091](https://doi.org/10.1785/0120040091).
- Moni, Aishwarya and Scott Rickard (2009). “Comparison of Localization Algorithms Using Attenuation Estimates”. In: *Digital Signal Processing Workshop and 5th IEEE Signal Processing Education Workshop, 2009. DSP/SPE 2009. IEEE 13th*. IEEE, pp. 42–47.
- Pirinen, T. W. (2006). “A Lattice Viewpoint for Direction of Arrival Estimation Using Quantized Time Differences of Arrival”. In: *Proc. IEEE ICASSP*.
- Pirinen, Tuomo, Pasi Pertilä, and Ari Visa (2003). “Toward intelligent sensors - reliability for time delay based direction of arrival estimates”. In: *Proc IEEE Intl. Conf. ASSP*. Vol. 5. IEEE, pp. V–197–200. DOI: [10.1109/ICASSP.2003.1199902](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICASSP.2003.1199902).
- Rosenberger, A. (2010). “Realtime Ground-Motion Analysis: Distinguishing P and S Arrivals in a Noisy Environment”. In: *Bull. Seism. Soc. Am.* 100.3, pp. 1252–1262. DOI: [10.1785/0120090265](https://doi.org/10.1785/0120090265).
- (2014). *Prototype Client Application for the Earthquake Early Warning Component of WARN*. Tech. rep. ONC, WARN Project.
- Rydelek, Paul and Kwang-Hee Kim (2010). “A study on feasibility of earthquake early warning in Korea: Determination of locations and magnitudes of events”. In: *Geosciences Journal* 14.1, pp. 41–47. DOI: [10.1007/s12303-010-0005-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12303-010-0005-5).
- Schau, H. C. and A. Z. Robinson (1987). “Passive source location employing intersecting spherical surfaces from time-of-arrival differences”. In: *IEEE Trans. ASSP* 35.8, pp. 1223–1225.
- Shao, Guangfu, Chen Ji, and Dapeng Zhao (2011). “Rupture process of the 9 March, 2011, Mw 7.4 Sanriku-Oki, Japan earthquake constrained by jointly inverting teleseismic waveforms, strong motion data and GPS observations”. In: *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 38.L00G20, p. 6. DOI: [10.1029/2011GL049164](https://doi.org/10.1029/2011GL049164).
- Vincenty, T. (1975). “Direct and inverse solutions of geodesics on the ellipsoid with application of nested equations”. In: *Surv. Rev* 22.176, pp. 88–93.
- Wei, He-Wen and Shang-Fu Ye (2008). “Comments on ”A linear closed form algorithm for source localization from time-differences of arrival””. In: *IEEE Signal Process. Lett.* 15, p. 895.
- Wu, Yih-Min et al. (2007). “Determination of earthquake early warning parameters, τ_c and P_d , for southern California”. In: *Geophys. J. Int.* 170, pp. 711–717. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-246X.2007.03430.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-246X.2007.03430.x).
- Wurman, G., R. M. Allen, and P. Lombard (2007). “Toward earthquake early warning in northern California”. In: *J. Geophys. Res.* 112. DOI: [10.1029/2006JB004830](https://doi.org/10.1029/2006JB004830).
- Yamada, M. and J. Mori (2009). “Using τ_c to estimate magnitude for earthquake early warning and effects of near field term”. In: *J. Geophys. Res.* 114.B05301. DOI: [10.1029/2008JB006080](https://doi.org/10.1029/2008JB006080).
- Yamamoto, Shunroku et al. (2008). “On the estimation of seismic intensity in earthquake early warning systems”. In: *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 35. see also: Rydelek and Kim, 2010. DOI: [10.1029/2007GL033034](https://doi.org/10.1029/2007GL033034).
- Zollo, A. et al. (2010). “A threshold-based earthquake early warning using dense accelerometer networks”. In: *Geophys. J. Int.* 183, pp. 963–974. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-246X.2010.04765.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-246X.2010.04765.x).